

FACTORS AFFECTING DECISION-MAKING PROCESS THAT LEADS TO CAREER UNCERTAINTY AMONG STEM STUDENTS IN MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY SULU

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ABSTRACT

Career uncertainty is a leading concern among senior high school students as they approach the change from high school to college education. This period marks a critical point in their lives, where they must make crucial decisions about their future career paths. The Purpose is to identify the components that influence the decision-making process of STEM students at Mindanao State University–Sulu during an occurrence of career uncertainty. It aimed to determine the following objectives: 1) to find out how do personal factors affect the decision-making process that leads to career uncertainty among STEM students at Mindanao State University-Sulu. 2) to determine how external factors affect the decision-making process that leads to career uncertainty among STEM students in Mindanao State University-Sulu and 3) to identify in what ways contextual factors affect the decision-making process that leads to career uncertainty among STEM students in Mindanao State University. The Method used was Face-to-face interviews were used for data gathering, and purposive sampling was applied in selecting the participants, where twenty (20) students from the Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School were selected, particularly the Grade 12 STEM students. The researchers employed interview questionnaires as instruments for the study to collect the necessary data. Moreover, the data were analysed using thematic analysis. The Findings revealed that career uncertainty is a complex issue influenced by the combination of personal, external, and contextual factors. Which have organized themes from the participants data. Factors affecting the decision-making process indeed have effects on the career decision-making

process of the Grade 12 STEM students in Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School.

Keywords: *Decision-making process, career uncertainty, financial limitations, passions, interests, job demands, senior high school, institutional availability, familial & peer influence*

INTRODUCTION

Career uncertainty is a leading concern among senior high school students as they approach the change from high school to college education. This period marks a critical point in their lives, where they must make crucial decisions about their future career paths. Moreover, the increasing complexity of jobs nowadays, paired with a wide variety of available career choices, often leaves students feeling overwhelmed and unsure about which path to take. This uncertainty can have a significant impact on their academic performance, mental well-being, and overall journey into adulthood. Azhenov (2023) research into the field of career uncertainty emphasizes a critical fact: the act of choosing a profession is not merely a decision but a reflection of one's ongoing relationship with their abilities, interests, and the broader professional world. This fact opens up a study into how we, as individuals and societies, understand professional identity and career development.

Career uncertainty refers to the state of indecision or lack of clarity experienced by individuals, particularly students or early-career professionals, regarding their future career paths. It includes uncertainty about an individual's interest, skills, values, and goals, as well as the uncertainty about the availability, stability and attainability of career choices in the present and future jobs. Career uncertainty may arise from many factors. One of which (Barayuga & Ramirez, 2020) stated that parents have significant internal influence when it comes to a child's decision to choose their current path over their ideal one. They also stated that the freshmen's doubts and uncertainties, the freshmen class's potential, and the school's vicinity were cited as the causes of these external choices for students.

In an age when the landscape of work is constantly reshaped by technological advancements and global shifts. As reported by Gati et al. (2019) a critical aspect of career selection: the need for individuals to adaptively navigate through a sea of information--often incomplete and rapidly changing--about potential career pathways. This problem is highlighted by the psychological aspects of profession selection, where self-doubt and a lack of confidence can cloud judgment and lead to selections that do not reflect one's genuine capabilities or objectives.

Individuals might experience both positive and bad consequences as a result of the career decision-making process. Studying decision-making processes in the context of career choices is important for understanding the complex factors that influence these decisions, applying theoretical models to real-world situations, and developing strategies that help individuals create information and fulfill career decisions. Understanding these

processes provides greater fulfillment at work, productivity, and long-term success. It also encourages self-awareness and adaptability in a constantly changing employment market.

Career decisions are heavily influenced by one's experiences and contextual factors. Group dynamics, promotion opportunities, and organizational commitment influence how individuals assess risks, set personal goals, process information, and evaluate alternatives, ultimately controlling their career paths (Pascariati & Ali, 2022).

Coping successfully with career decision issues in senior high school contributes to successful choice implementation in higher education, including option actualization, academic adjustment, and commitment to the chosen study. On the other side, dysfunctional thinking and unconscious processes may influence the logic of job selection and prevent some possibilities from occurring. Understanding students' perspectives on professional decision-making is important for educators who want to assist them effectively. Educators can adapt their advice and support to students by learning about their values, experiences, and specific ambitions.

A variety of factors influence student's decision-making ability. According to Estigoy et al. (2022), the variables that had the greatest influence on students' decision-making were personal preferences and self-evaluations, decision-making confidence, work market practicality, and social and familial expectations. These components differ based on the individual, but they are generally applicable to the majority of students.

Personal, external, and contextual factors are several types of influences that might contribute to students' career uncertainty. Personal factors are individual characteristics and attributes that might influence a student's career decision-making process, including interests and values, self-efficacy, personality traits, health and well-being, and academic performance. External factors are elements that are beyond the individual's control that may influence their employment decisions and uncertainty, such as family influence, peer influence, socioeconomic status, teacher guidance, and educational resources. Contextual factors influencing students' job decisions include their geographic location, cultural expectations, economic situations, and school environment. Understanding these factors can help identify the underlying causes of students' career uncertainty and may guide interventions to help them make professional decisions.

Research on career uncertainty among STEM students has mostly focused on aspects such as interpersonal and interpersonal relationships, work passion, and self-efficacy, as well as the significance of STEM profession exposure and students' comprehension of STEM disciplines. However, there are limitations in studying the experiential aspects of career uncertainty and decision-making processes in STEM students. While previous studies provide useful information, more research is needed in this area.

In this research paper, we will examine the factors contributing to career uncertainty among senior high school students and explore its implications. By gaining a

deeper understanding of the challenges the students face and identifying effective interventions, we can better support their career development and facilitate smoother transitions into the working society.

Research Questions

The study's goal is to investigate the factors that influence the decision-making process of STEM students at Mindanao State University-Sulu during periods of career uncertainty. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How do personal factors affect decision-making process which leads to uncertainty in choosing career to be pursued?
2. How do external factors affect decision-making process which leads to uncertainty in choosing career to be pursued?
3. In what ways do contextual factors affect decision-making process which leads to uncertainty in choosing career to be pursued?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

As stated by Tenny et al. (2017), qualitative research investigates and provides deeper insights into real-world situations; it collects people's experiences, attitudes, and behaviour; and it answers the how's, whys, and what's rather than how many or how much. This study followed a phenomenological research design. Phenomenology is a branch of philosophy that emphasizes the study of life experiences of individuals as well as the state or configuration of their consciousness. The researchers used this research design to determine the factors that influence the decision-making process with career uncertainty. The researchers distributed questionnaires and conducted interviews with participants to collect data.

Research Site

The study was conducted at Mindanao State University Sulu-Senior High School. The school is located at Barangay Bangkal Capitol Site Patikul, Sulu. It is a university school that was established in 2016. Mindanao State University–Sulu stands as a beacon of educational excellence. Located among the scenic landscapes and rich cultural heritage of Sulu, the university provides a nurturing environment for academic growth and personal development

Participants

STEM students who are currently enrolled at Mindanao State University–Sulu in the academic year 2024-2025 are the study's chosen participants. A total of 20 Grade 12 students were gathered, ranging from STEM 1 to 5, with each section having 4 participants.

Research Instrument

In this study, face-to-face interviews were used. The researcher employed essay and interview questionnaires as instruments for the study to collect the necessary data. Instead of using random sampling, the researchers applied the non-probability purposive sampling and judgment to select participants that were suitable for the study. Participants were able to communicate their feelings and experiences concerning their future decisions, which was the most effective method of data exploration.

Data Collection

After the questionnaires were validated, the researchers wrote a letter of consent to the school director, STEM coordinator, and the advisers of the grade 12 STEM students. When approved, the researchers then proceeded to search for the study's respondents and personally carried out the interview. The researchers agreed to keep the participant's identity anonymous and vowed to never disclose it to anyone. After

finishing the interview, the researchers gathered and carefully analyzed the collected data.

Data Analysis

The technique used to analyze the study is thematic analysis, as it allowed the researchers to explore and interpret the quality and depth of the gathered data. Clarke and Braun (2017) stated that it is a method for analyzing, identifying, and reporting patterns within the data. Thus, it was deemed suitable for the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section examines deeper the factors affecting the decision-making process that led to career uncertainty in coded, analysed, and organized participant data into themes.

Personal Factors

A person's future is greatly influenced by their career choice, yet many people experience uncertainty during this process. Personal factors that influence career decisions include interest, passion, fear, and self-doubt. Interest can either be a clarity or create confusion, leading to indecision and anxiety about the future. Ajayi et al. (2023) stated, Career interest is the process by which people discover, explore, and examine their interests before choosing a career decision. However, most people find it difficult to choose the right career because transforming personal interests into practical careers can be overwhelming sometimes.

What are your primary interests and passions?

I'm interested in math and I love numbers, so I want to pursue accountancy. (P3, Excerpt 1)

My primary interest since I was in junior high is to take medical courses in college. (P5, Excerpt 2)

My interest is to pursue my childhood dream to become a civil engineering. I know I'm not good in drawing, but I know math. (P16, Excerpt 3)

I don't have any particular interest because I'm still undecided what career path should I choose. (P11, Excerpt 4)

Career choices are influenced by personal interest, strength, and past experiences. Based on the participants' views, some students have a strong vision for their future, while others are still exploring option and uncertain. According to Nyamwange 2016, his study concludes that having prior information about a career is important to develop and nurture in the career to be pursue

I'm really passionate when it comes to speaking; I love it when speaking in front of a lot of people. (P1, Excerpt 5)

Law will always be my passion; I love learning and am passionate about it. (P2, Excerpt 6)

My passion is to always be an engineer, but they want me to take pharmacy. (P7, Excerpt 7)

The participants statements show that some students are confident to pursue their passion, while others face external problem that may conflict with their true passions. According to Marathe & Wagani 2022, The study demonstrated that when selecting a profession is concerned, passion takes back seat due to the perceived stability, insecurity, and uncertainty in such offbeat careers.

Do you consider your fears and phobias when deciding your career course?

Even if I'm passionate about public speaking, I sometimes feel fear especially about being judged. (P1, Excerpt 8)

I want to pursue related to medical course but I have phobias on bloods, injection, and operation. (P5, Excerpt 9)

It's hard for me to speak publicly and I get frighten when facing many people in front. (P8, Excerpt 10)

I fear the uncertainty in my decision in life and overthinking if this will gonna be good or bad for me. (P15, Excerpt 11)

Everytime we pursue something there would always be hardship and we should be ready to face those fears. (P6, Excerpt 12)

I'm willing to learn and fight my fears for my dreams. (P9, Excerpt 13)

The participants statements express a journey of overcoming fears while fear because fears are natural in human to experience it. Fear feels like reality and the willingness to face these fears is key to achieving success. According to Hanks (2018) Understandings the consequences of fear decreased decision-making skills and altered perceptions. Commitment provides opportunities to differentiate between fear of commitment and fear of failure.

Do you consider your capabilities when making your decision?

Sometimes I think if I can do this course or give up on it. (P15, Excerpt 14)

It seems like I'm not ready to face college life. (P17, Excerpt 15)

I can't say I'm capable enough because I'm not smart and not good enough in a analysation. (P9, Excerpt 16)

It could be difficult for me, if this is lacking for me I will not choose it. (P4, Excerpt 17)

Based on the participants' narratives, some students experience self-doubt regarding their academic abilities and readiness for college. Encouraging students with a growth mindset and believing abilities can improve with effort. Salvador (2011) states, doubt is often considered as an unpleasant experience that should be avoided. Doubt becomes a process that allows people to either progress and develop or remain stagnant. Additionally, Self-doubt is one of three factors with less satisfying relationship, defined within the larger view of relational uncertainty (Knobloch, 2008)

External Factors

External factors influence an individual's decision-making process, particularly when selecting a career path. The economic job market, technological advancements, and practicality can all result in uncertainty and pressure. As stated by Sarwar & Azmat (2013), Job security and salary benefits are economic concerns that attract individuals to career in the right way, and the study shown that people are satisfied with this part of the job. On the other hand, due to the lack of right guidance, students often fail to choose the right picture of today's economy. Moreover, Humayon et al. (2018) stated that it is true the country's economic growth is connected to a rise in employment rates and people's increasing spends capacity.

How do current job market trends and employment opportunities influence your choices?

As long as I get a high salary and good project experience. (P6, Excerpt 18)

Many people apply to be teachers, but even Latin honors aren't always accepted because of the competitiveness and depend on connections. (P1, Excerpt 19)

Criminology is famous course and many students choose it. (P15, Excerpt 20)

Pharmacy is lesser around in the province. (P7, Excerpt 21)

The job market shows me how creative work are in demand here in the country. (P14, Excerpt 22)

The participants statements present various perspectives on career choices, job market and industry trends. Many individuals considering financial stability and skill development when selecting a job. Some are securing employment is not always based on merit but by competitive and connections. While others obtain it by the popularity and demands. Khalid & Ahmad (2021) reveals that students choose these jobs for a variety of reasons, including social issues, employability, social expectations demands, and personal curiosity.

How do technological advancements and innovations in your field impact your decisions?

It impacts my career decision in a way that it makes me more eager to determine and to get that career choice. (P1, Excerpt 23)

Technological advancements give me inspiration and motivation to really pursue what career I really want. (P10, Excerpt 24)

Some students are more dependent on using technology, and it affects their critical thinking. (P16, Excerpt 25)

It can break your image and can affect the way you think like the toxicity of social media nowadays. (P7, Excerpt 26)

I need to constantly adapt and learn to stay relevant, which adds to my uncertainty when choosing a career. (P14, Excerpt 27)

The participants' statements highlight the complex relationship between technology and career decision-making. While technology offers opportunity for advancement, it also brings challenges that students must overcome when determining their future career. Kumi et al. (2024) emphasizes the importance of specific strategies that take into account the unique environment of developing countries, ensuring that technological advancements result in concrete career growth opportunities for individuals. Additionally, Technology has a huge impact on workplace, increasing the demand for cognitive and digital skills. To address these challenges, strategies like time and attention management, self-discipline in disconnecting from work, and reflecting on responsiveness during overtime are important. Adaptability and willingness to learn new technologies are essential for career growth (Beer & Mulder 2020).

Do you consider the job demands when making your decision? How?

Without the need of people, immerse yourself in pursuing your career. (P2, Excerpt 28)

If you're not passionate about something, it's really hard. (P3, Excerpt 29)

Engineering is a tough battle, and we all know that there are only several students who actually passed. (P11, Excerpt 30)

Choosing a career path where there are plenty of opportunities is a good strategy. (P13, Excerpt 31)

If there's an opportunity, we can work immediately. (P18, Excerpt 32)

Based on the participants statements, pursuing a career demands dedication and passion, as it can be difficult to achieve without practicality. Ocon (2023) state that following a practical job path will bring greater benefits than choosing a career path based solely on passion. Considering job satisfaction, career stability, and work-life balance. Individuals who take pragmatic approach to employment selection can better position themselves to attain personal and professional goals . Moreover, Immersing oneself in a chosen job without relying on others promotes personal growth and achievement. Balancing passion and practicality is important when choosing a career path. Students can prepare for a successful and fulfilling career by evaluating their interests and assessing the employment market (Rahman 2024).

Contextual Factors

Does your financial situation influence your career decision-making process?

Even though teaching is my passion, there is a part of me that still wants to pursue psychology. However, due to my financial situation, I might not be able to afford medical courses, as additional education is required after earning an undergraduate degree in psychology. So, it seems like I'll just end up being a teacher because, even if we're good at something, if we can't afford it, it's no use. I'm not saying psychology is my second choice, but if I had the chance and the money, I would definitely pursue psychology. (P1, Excerpt 33)

Even if I want to pursue my preferred course, I know that my parents can't afford the tuition since we're financially poor. (P10, Excerpt 34)

Actually, from what I understand. Civil engineering requires high cost to study (i.e, one needs to study overseas since the institutions with BSCE within Sulu are limited). So we do need to consider our financial situation. (P12, Excerpt 35)

I fear that what if I can't pursue it because of our financial situation. If my parents can't afford it then I won't pursue it. (P7, Excerpt 36)

I do consider our financial situation, Because studying architecture is very expensive. Namely, the materials you need to study architecture and the tuition. (P6, Excerpt 37)

The statements above indicate that financial situations play a significant role in the decision-making processes of students. As Senara et al.'s (2024) study emphasized, the financial considerations play a vital role in shaping career choices, demonstrating how financial factors have a significant impact on many career-related decisions. Nevertheless, Their study declared that while financial factors are important, they do not solely determine career choices. As such, elements such as institutional availability, familial pressure and support, and the roles of peers also play major roles in shaping a student's decision. Below are the participants' stances regarding the availability of institutions within Sulu:

Does the availability of institutional support contribute to the uncertainty in your career choices? How?

Since nursing is already available here in MSU-Sulu, it further solidified my decision to pursue it. (P9, Excerpt 38)

Currently, I think the only college that offers civil engineering here in Sulu is SCT. However, next year, MSU-Sulu will open a civil engineering program. So yes, we do need to consider the institutional availability within Sulu, as I think the BSCE program at SCT is not as advanced compared to other schools. Therefore, we might actually need to go to other places to access better programs. (P12, Excerpt 39)

The schools within Sulu that offer the BS Pharmacy program is limited, I think only Notre Dame and MSU have it. But at the time when I made my decision to pursue pharmacy, I

didn't know MSU had one. So I was hesitant to pursue it since studying at Notre Dame is very expensive. But when I found out that MSU offers pharmacy. I thought "Ahh, since MSU offers pharmacy, I'll just study here." (P18, Excerpt 39)

It does affect my decision, since there is no college here in Sulu that offers architecture. (P6, Excerpt 40)

It really does affect me. Because I'm not sure if I'm going to pass my entrance test. And there is no school here in Sulu that offers my chosen program. (P4, Excerpt 41)

Institutional and geographical accessibility significantly influences students' career decision-making processes, as highlighted by the participants' statements. The availability of specific programs, such as nursing at MSU-Sulu, often solidifies students' choices, while limited options, like the absence of architecture programs in Sulu, can hinder aspirations. As stated by Cullinan and Flannery (2021), geographic accessibility plays a crucial role in shaping higher education participation decisions, with travel distance acting as a significant deterrent for many students, particularly those from lower-income backgrounds. In addition, families also greatly influence students' career choices. Some parents push for specific fields, while others support their children's decisions:

How does your family influence your career decisions?

When it comes to career decisions, my mom just goes with the flow, but one thing she really wants for me is teaching. So I said, okay, I'll just be a teacher because there's a part of me that really wants to be a teacher, and I think I'm more passionate about teaching, it's not heavy for me. My aunts also influenced my decision, one said I should study law, the other said accountancy, but I'll follow my mom. (P1, Excerpt 42)

Actually, they're the ones telling me to take a medical course, but I don't have any interest in it. If I were the one deciding, I would always choose engineering. (P7, Excerpt 43)

Yes, because, for me, my parents have the right to choose my course. When they told me that they also wanted me to pursue engineering, that's why I started considering it as well. (P13, Excerpt 44)

Actually, my family is very supportive. No matter what I choose for my career, they will always back me up wholeheartedly. (P2, Excerpt 45)

My parents are working hard to pay for my school bills. This inspires me to pursue what I truly want, and they always remind me to believe in myself, saying, "We are always here to support you." (P9, Excerpt 46)

On my mother's side, many of them are in nursing. I was influenced by this when I was younger. Nursing not only helps the community but also benefits us by allowing us to stay closer to home. (P5, Excerpt 47)

My family is struggling financially and cannot afford to send me to Zamboanga. Additionally, my grandmother is bedridden, and the thought of leaving them behind pains me deeply. (P6, Excerpt 48)

Financial situations and family needs, such as caring for a sick relative, also play a big role. Overall, family support and circumstances also shape students' career paths significantly. In the words of Koçak et al. (2021), families significantly influence students' career decision-making by providing emotional and financial support, sharing knowledge, and instilling values that shape career preferences. Parents serve as role models, and their educational background can enhance students' confidence in career choices. However, high parental expectations may also create stress, impacting students' career decision-making self-efficacy and overall happiness. In addition to this, peers and friends can also influence the decisions of an individual. Below are the roles of peers in influencing the participants' decisions in choosing their career.

Do your friends influence your career decisions? How?

Of course, my friends influence my career choices. I have a friend from GAS 1 and as I mentioned earlier, I wanted to pursue criminology. She told me that if I focused on criminology, she would be left alone in the nursing department, and that motivated me to explore nursing. (P2, Excerpt 49)

Yes, as grade 12 students, we already share our plans with each other so that we will never drift apart. (P15, Excerpt 50)

Yes, it does. My other friends are also taking medical courses, and I was influenced by their actions and how they help their families. (P5, Excerpt 51)

Yes, my friends are indeed influencing me because we actually have the same career goals. As we discussed topics like the advantages of being a nurse, it motivated me to do my best. (P10, Excerpt 52)

Yes, for example my friend is taking a medical course, and I also wanted to take a medical course like psychology, I wanted to be a doctor. It still affects me, while I might feel a little envious of her ability to pursue her medical aspirations, nevertheless I'll still pursue teaching. (P1, Excerpt 53)

They won't influence me either because I'm not interested in what they suggest. (P3, Excerpt 54)

No, because I will always stick to what my family wants me to pursue. (P7, Excerpt 55)

No, my friends have nothing to do with my career decisions. (P11, Excerpt 56)

No, they cannot influence my career decision. (P12, Excerpt 57)

No. Because this course is not what I wanted when I was a child until now, and my friends don't influence me to choose criminology as a course. (P14, Excerpt 58)

Friends play a significant but varied role in students' career decision-making processes, as highlighted by the participants. Some students acknowledged that their friends influenced their choices, whether through shared goals, encouragement, or the desire to stay connected. While others emphasized that their career decisions were not influenced by friends, as they prioritized personal interests, family expectations, or long-

held aspirations. As supported by Mtemeri's study (2020) that found that peer interactions significantly impact career choices, primarily through peer advice, encouragement, and education. Students often share critical information about careers, such as salary expectations, working conditions, and educational pathways. However, they generally do not seek validation for their decisions from peers.

Conclusions

The influences encountered by students in deciding their career can mainly be categorized into three parts: personal, external, and contextual. Personal factors include an individual's interests, passions, fears, and self-doubt. External factors involve economic conditions, job market trends, and technological advancement. Contextual factors are the influence of their financial situation, accessibility, family, and friends.

In the context of personal factors, many students have clear goals based on their passion, while others struggle to decide due to conflicting interests, limited experience, and indecision. Additionally, fear of failure, future uncertainties, and personal insecurities also contribute to the hesitation of students to decide. Phobia-related fears also play a role in some of the students' decisions. Nevertheless, many students express their willingness to overcome their fears. This willingness to confront these fears emerges as a critical factor in overcoming their uncertainties.

External factors, likewise, are a major influence on students' career uncertainty. Many students would prioritize job availability and financial stability over their passion. The rapid advancement of technology creates both opportunities and challenges, with some students finding motivation through digital advancements while others face distractions and social media pressures. This illustrates the need for students' adaptability and management. Not only that, competition among jobs also adds pressure, making the process more difficult, emphasizing the need for students' versatility and continuous learning to remain relevant in the advancing industries.

Finally, contextual factors such as financial limitations often force students to compromise on their preferred career. Many students face financial constraints that limit their career options, forcing them to pursue a more affordable career. Moreover, the availability of programs within their locations either allows them or restricts their choices, as limited program availability in Sulu affects students' ability to study their preferred courses. Meanwhile, family expectations and support play two roles: either providing encouragement for some or creating pressures for others. In like manner, peers can serve as sources of motivation or distraction, depending on the strength of an individual's conviction.

Overall, career uncertainty is a complex issue influenced by the combination of personal, external, and contextual factors. Tackling these issues requires effective career guidance, familiarity with many career paths, and emotional support from families. Providing students with the right knowledge, resources, and self-confidence can help them navigate their career paths with greater clarity and certainty, ultimately leading to more satisfying career choice.

Recommendations

Career Guidance. In helping students handle career uncertainty it is essential to enhance career guidance. School should improve their guidance programs by offering personalized career evaluation, workshops, and one-on-one sessions with career counselors. As stated by Azhenov et al. (2023), Students who receive career counselling are guaranteed a smooth transition from college to the working world. Career preparation is a plan for developing a career as well as personal beliefs, attitudes, motivation, feelings, abilities, behaviors, and activities that will lead to successful professional advancements. A successful career is one that meets to the individual's expectations.

Self-Exploration. Many students face fear and self-doubt when making career decisions, which causes to hesitation and undecided. According to Ran et al. (2023) Students should actively explore and reflect to find and realize calling in order to establish a solid foundation for developing their adaptability and subjective well-being. Career exploration and self-reflection can support the development of career adaptability and subjective well-being. Moreover, Career exploration and self-reflection can help gather information from a various source, boosting confidence in choosing a career and building up relevant resources (Taveira & Moreno 2003).

Economic Opportunity. When choosing a career, students are often influenced by job market trends and financial problems. Students can acquire real-world experience and develop skills by being exposed to real-world career opportunities. Suhi et al. (2022) and Arbab et al. (2022) state that students' career decisions are greatly influenced by interest and perceived job market demand, demonstrating that economic factors such as job availability can have a powerful impact on the career path. This is also supported by studies of Ashour (2016) and Al-Waqfi et al. (2023), when seeking to understand how people make career decisions, it is important to include external environments such as cultural norms and economic opportunities.

Institutional Availability and Accessibility. Sulu's institutions have limited program offering, limiting students' career options. Expanding its degree programs to include more STEM-related fields by providing students with online learning options or exchange programs that allow them to study their preferred courses. As stated by Siddiky & Akter (2021) Higher education institutions are factories that produce skilled human resources by imparting, creating, and disseminating knowledge and providing advanced education in a wide range of areas, resulting in increased productivity, business earnings, and economic growth, and are thus critical for Bangladesh's economic development, as well as other countries.

Family and Peer Support Systems. While some students receive strong support from family, others face pressure to follow the career paths dictated by their parents these factors significantly influence students' career choices. Moreover, peer support should be created by establishing positive environment where students can discuss career concerns and receive encouragement. As Chak-keung and Liu (2010) reveals that families have significant influence over their children's career decisions, which can be either positive or

negative. Additionally, Boye (2024) states that students' decision-making is also influenced by their peers as they look to their peers for acknowledgement and connection.

Technological Readiness. Both as a source of distraction and as a tool for discovery, technology is one of the major factor in choosing a career. Workshops on digital literacy, time management, and flexibility should be provided by schools to make sure that students can use technology to improve their career choices without getting overwhelmed by digital distraction. Career and technical education (CTE) is work-based curriculum that includes a series of courses that offer students with technical skills and information, preparing them for jobs and postsecondary education in high-demand professions. Suarta et al. (2017) emphasized the Higher education institutions must plan and implement educational programs to create graduates who not only have technical skills relates to their career, but also interpersonal skills that match the needs and expectations of employers.

For Future Researchers. More research into the long-term career effects of STEM graduates in conflict-affected provinces like Sulu. In similarly to the study of Lent et al. (2018), Future studies could apply longitudinal designs to explore the influence of various early career experiences such as: mentorship, internships, counseling to establish if early experience impacts retention, job satisfaction, and career stability in the careers of STEM students. Future research will utilise mixed methods designs to collect quantitative data on career outcomes as well as qualitative data on students' changing attitudes towards STEM careers (Fouad and Santana, 2017). Additionally, examining gender inequalities in career decision-making that affect STEM students within cultural contexts. As stated by Wang & Degol (2017) to learn about the societal expectations, self-efficacy, and institutional challenges that affect both male and female students with career uncertainty by examining the gender differences in career decision-making of STEM students

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Following research ethics regulations, the researchers are devoted to protecting the participants' privacy and confidentiality. The respondents' identity was also ensured by not disclosing their names or personal information during the research, complying with RA 10173, often known as the Data Privacy Act. Moreover, to acquire the selected participant's approval, the researchers explain all the study's key features, including its aim and purpose. Only relevant findings that will contribute to the study and support answers to the research questions were presented.

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